

COMPASS

Data Management Plan Deliverable 6.5

30th April 2024

Deliverable 6.5 – Data Management Plan

Title	Data Management Plan
Lead Beneficiary	Deltares
Lead Author(s)	Anaïs Couasnon (Deltares), Natalia Aleksandrova (Deltares)
Contributors	Dominik Paprotny (PIK), Christopher Jack (RCCC), Rachel Perks (MetOffice), Dan Bernie (MetOffice)
Deliverable number	D6.5
Work Package	WP6: Project management
Submission date	30/04/2024

Dissemination Level

PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online)	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
CI	EU classified — Restreint-UE/EU-Restricted, Confidential-UE/EU-Confidential, Secret-UE/EU-Secret under Decision 2015/444	

Version history

Date	Ver.	Contributors	Comment
2024-04-10	0.1	Natalia Aleksandrova, Anaïs Couasnon	First version ready for internal review
2024-04-26	0.1rev	Dominik Paprotny, Christopher Jack, Rachel Perks, Dan Bernie	Internal review
2024-04-30	1.0	Dan Bernie	Final review and first finished version ready

Citation

Couasnon A., Aleksandrova N. (2024): Data Management Plan. Horizon Europe project COMPASS. Deliverable D6.5.

The COMPASS project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101135481

Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable does not reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Responsibility for the information and views expressed herein lies entirely with the author(s).

Executive summary

This document is the deliverable 6.5 Data Management Plan (DMP) and presents the first version of the COMPASS Data Management Plan. An updated and finalized version of this deliverable will be presented in M34. The DMP describes the overall strategy for managing the data collected, used, modified, and generated during the project. The DMP is a living document, reviewed and updated during the project period, aiming to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) according to the FAIR principles. This will be supported with implementation according to the relevant OGC standards. In addition, the DMP will provide information on the measures to be taken to guarantee the protection, privacy and security of (sensitive) data during the entire lifecycle of the project.

This document also provides a preliminary and non-exhaustive list of some of the data that are planned to be used in the project. A more detailed list of the datasets will be provided within WP1, WP2 and WP3 through deliverables D1.1, D2.1, D2.2, D3.1, D3.4. More specifically, WP1, WP2 and WP3 include activities for identifying the datasets best suited to model compound extremes, describe compound extreme climate hazards for attribution studies and weather types and exposure datasets at different scales. We will therefore not provide a full list of data used in the project in this deliverable, but rather provide a reference to the specific deliverable where appropriate. This deliverable is primarily targeted at the consortium partners and should serve as a reference for the management of data products used in the project. It also serves to support the development of new data products in the project. All COMPASS project partners should refer to this plan to ensure a consistent approach to the sharing and documentation of the various datasets (including metadata).

Table of Contents

Executive summary	3
Acronym list.....	5
1. Data summary	6
1.1. Data collection and production	6
1.2. Data description	6
1.1.1. Hazard data.....	7
1.1.2. Exposure and vulnerability data	9
1.3. Purpose of the data beyond COMPASS project	9
2. FAIR data.....	9
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	9
2.2. Making data openly accessible.....	10
2.3. Making data interoperable.....	10
2.4. Increase data re-use	10
3. Other research outputs	11
4. Allocation of resources.....	12
5. Data security.....	13
6. Conclusion	14

Acronym list

CDS – Copernicus Climate Data Store

CERRA (-Land) - Copernicus European Regional ReAnalysis (over land)

CF – Climate and Forecasting

CMIP – Coupled Model Intercomparison Project

CORDEX – Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment

CP-RCM – Convention Permitting Regional Climate Models

DMP – Data Management plan

EFAS – The European Flood Awareness System

ERA5 - global atmospheric reanalysis dataset from ECMWF (fifth version)

EU – European Union

EUCP – European Climate Prediction project

FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

GLOFAS – Global Flood Awareness System

ISIMIP - Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project

JRC – Joint Research Center of the European Commission

NetCDF - Network Common Data Form

NUTS - Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics

OGC - Open Geospatial Consortium

UERRA – Uncertainties in Ensembles of Regional ReAnalysis

UKCP – UK Climate Projections

WMO – World Meteorological Organisation

WP – Work Package

1. Data summary

1.1. Data collection and production

There is a large and continuously increasing quantity of open-source data that can be used in the modelling of natural hazards under climate change and their associated risks and impacts. In COMPASS we strive to use as much as possible open-source data that can be easily accessed from existing online portals, repositories, and services. The project will prioritize re-using the already vast number of high-quality available datasets over the creation of new ones whenever possible.

The main source for global and European data will be the datasets hosted by the Copernicus Services, such as the Climate Data Store (CDS), Marine Data Store and Emergency Management Service. Other relevant data repositories and hubs that will be used in the project include (but are not limited to) the Joint Research Centre's (JRC) Risk Data Hub, The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP) and World Climate Research Program's Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP).

New data will be generated in the project in the context of the dedicated modelling for the use cases, including hazard and impact-related time-series, maps, and statistics that are of relevance to complex extremes attribution. All data that will be developed within COMPASS will be published in appropriate open-access data repositories, such as Zenodo or Pangea. Every new dataset uploaded will be accompanied with the appropriate open-access license and required metadata. Where applicable we will follow CF Conventions, for example for NetCDF files, and FAIR Principles.

The complete list of the datasets generated by COMPASS will be added to this document at a later stage and finalized at the end of the project. The datasets that are already envisioned as part of the COMPASS deliverables are:

- Dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas (WP1)
- Dataset on weather types and large-scale climate drivers (WP2)
- Counterfactual dataset of tropical cyclone-affected areas (WP2)
- Exposure dataset at multiple scales (WP3)
- Data for the impact and climate attribution studies for each of the use cases (WP4), if not already included by the previous datasets.

1.2. Data description

We aim to collect and generate the relevant data for assessing hazards and risks from compound events under climate change, including climatological, hydrological and oceanographic data, results of environmental model simulations, observation data, exposure and vulnerability data. Main datasets identified at the beginning of the project are on global and European scale, and local-scale datasets are expected to be used in the context of the use cases. WP1 has the task of identifying the relevant datasets that can be reused for characterizing compound extremes (hazard data) but also the generation of new datasets by using these datasets in relevant models to obtain impact data. For example, the dataset of tropical cyclone affected areas. WP2 will identify the best currently available climate datasets to perform attribution of complex extremes and produce a new datasets on weather types and large-scale climate drivers. WP3 is tasked with generating new datasets for exposure at multiple scales, currently missing. The project will therefore both be using existing datasets but also generate new datasets. We briefly describe next the existing datasets we are expecting to use for the hazard, exposure and vulnerability data.

1.1.1. Hazard data

Where possible, we will make use of global- to continental scale datasets that are hosted by Copernicus Services, such as the Climate Data Store, Marine Data Store, Emergency Management Service and Copernicus satellite products. Relevant global / European scale datasets are ERA5, CORDEX, CMIP and potentially PRIMAVERA, H2020 EUCP, TIGGE¹, STORM² and Sentinel products.

Additional high-resolution data is available from project partners Met Office (UKCP) and Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK), and new datasets will possibly be available under DestinationEarth (resulting amongst others from high-resolution CP-RCMs).

Among all options for obtaining climate data, we will prioritize the use of the latest generation of climate simulations (CMIP6, CORDEX, EUCP, HighResMIP, Copernicus and possibly DestinationEarth) at regional to continental scales to benefit from most up to date model developments and allow for the transferability of our method to other locations other than the case studies.

Local data in the form of in-situ observations (meteorological observations, tide gauges) will also be used in the context of the use cases.

Data sources for this type of data will be identified during the project and added to this document.

Some of the mentioned datasets that will potentially be used are described below. Most datasets are in NetCDF format.

1.1.1.1. Historical climate datasets

ERA5 and ERA5-Land reanalysis are the global atmospheric reanalysis datasets produced by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). Reanalysis combines model data with observations from across the world into a globally complete and consistent dataset using the laws of physics. The datasets provide a comprehensive view of the Earth's atmosphere, for the period 1940 to present for ERA5 (0.25° resolution) and 1959 to present for ERA5 -Land (0.1° resolution). Both reanalysis data sets are widely used in climate research, weather forecasting, and other applications. ERA5 also includes an ensemble component at half the resolution to provide information on the synoptic uncertainty of its products. ERA5-land parameter uncertainty currently can be accessed using the equivalent ERA5 fields.

Other historical datasets that could be used and considered are E-OBS, UERRA, CERRA, if they provide a better characterization of compound extremes. In WP2 datasets of historical weather patterns will also be used³.

1.1.1.2. Future climate datasets

CORDEX regional climate data is a dataset of high-resolution regional climate model simulations for Europe, produced by a consortium of European research institutions. The dataset provides projections of future climate change at a regional scale, with a resolution of at least 25 km. EURO-CORDEX data covers the period from 1950 to 2100 and is used in climate research, impact assessments, and adaptation planning at the regional level.

¹ THORPEX Interactive Grand Global Ensemble

² Bloemendaal, N., Haigh, I. D., de Moel, H., Muis, S., Haarsma, R. J., & Aerts, J. C. (2020). Generation of a global synthetic tropical cyclone hazard dataset using STORM. *Scientific data*, 7(1), 40.

³ Neal, R. (2022). Daily historical weather pattern classifications for the UK and surrounding European area (1950 to 2020). PANGAEA. <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.942896>.

CMIP5 and **CMIP6** climate data are global climate model simulations produced by international research institutions as part of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (**CMIP**). The datasets provide projections of historical periods and future climate change under different scenarios of greenhouse gas emissions. CMIP5 data covers the period from 1850 to 2100, while CMIP6 data covers the period from 1850 to 2300.

1.1.1.3. High-resolution datasets

Projects such as the **H2020 EUCP**, **Destination Earth** and **PRIMAVERA** aim to produce high-resolution (i.e. typically 2-3 km resolution) and well evaluated climate data, vital to obtain more accurate and robust predictions for future climate extremes at the local scale. This could be for example, of particular importance for the case studies. For example, having a finer resolution also directly improves the representation of small scale weather phenomena such as tropical cyclones.

PRIMAVERA has performed a series of experiments runs, atmosphere-only and coupled runs, for the period 1950 until 2050. The data is already accessible as part of the CMIP6 model intercomparison. In the future, the runs may be extended to go until 2100.

H2020 EUCP has performed convection permitting model runs for various domains across Europe. The ensemble runs provide datasets bridges current climate data to near future prediction (next 10 years) and up to 40 years ahead.

National climate projections can provide high resolution datasets of climate variables and will be used for some of the case studies. For example, for the United Kingdom, **the UKCP** provides climate projections up to year 2100 for the climate variables over land and up to year 2300 for projections of mean sea levels at various spatial resolution. The finest high-resolution datasets have a spatial resolution of about 2.2 km.

DestinationEarth aim is to provide a digital twin model of the Earth and therefore an accurate and high-resolution global model among others for climate and weather simulations.

1.1.1.4. Tropical cyclone datasets

IBTrACS (International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship) project is the most complete global collection of historical tropical cyclones available. It merges recent and historical tropical cyclone data from multiple agencies to create a unified, publicly available, best-track dataset that improves inter-agency comparisons. IBTrACS was developed collaboratively with WMO Regional Specialized Meteorological Centres, as well as other organizations and individuals from around the world.

The **STORM** dataset contains synthetic tropical cyclone tracks. The dataset consists of 10,000 years of synthetic tropical cyclone tracks, generated using the Synthetic Tropical cyclOne geneRation Model (STORM) algorithm (see Bloemendaal et al, 2022). The dataset is generated using historical data from IBTrACS and represents present-climate conditions. For example, the data can be used to calculate tropical cyclone risk in coastal regions prone to tropical cyclones.

1.1.1.1. Other datasets

TIGGE is an ensemble forecast dataset starting from 2006. It provides global weather forecasts from 1 day and up to 2 weeks ahead, and for one member up to 32 days ahead. The ensemble forecasts runs allows for probabilistic predictions of the very near future.

Depending on the specific needs for the case studies, other datasets such as hydrological datasets may be useful. For example, gridded discharge datasets are available for Europe at daily to subdaily time scales (**EFAS**) or global scale (**GLOFAS**) through the CDS.

1.1.2. Exposure and vulnerability data

Accurate data on historical and future exposure to climate hazards is needed to analyze the impacts and develop improved approaches to impact attribution. Exposure datasets at multiple spatial and temporal scales are needed. In COMPASS the existing datasets will be used where possible, but also new datasets will be developed, information on which will be added to this document in the course of the project.

Existing large-scale datasets commonly used for exposure are Open Street Map (**OSM**), a vector-based and continuously updated map of geodata objects, such as buildings, roads, etc. The **CORINE** land cover dataset provides a harmonized land cover and land use dataset for Europe. It is available since 1990 and updated every 6 years.

The primary sources of high-quality global and European data will be the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (**ISIMIP**) and data published at CDS and JRC Risk Data Hub. The HANZE database will be used as a basis for developing new European datasets. **HANZE** database of exposure is based on a pan-European, high-resolution exposure model⁴ and is heavily based on Copernicus and other EU-enabled datasets (e.g. CORINE Land Cover, European Settlement Map, GEOSTAT population, NUTS3-level statistics by Eurostat).

In developing new exposure datasets, particularly the latest public historical and projected data will be integrated, sourced from Eurostat, UN, IMF and national sources.

Vulnerability data will be obtained by using openly available data and methods where possible. The aim will be to avoid complex software for this purpose, to avoid including elements of the modelling chain that could not be then disseminated with an open license. Simpler methods, even if not as accurate as those complex models, will be preferred if they enable open sharing of data and code.

1.3. Purpose of the data beyond COMPASS project

The data generated within the COMPASS project will not only contribute to a new and advanced approach on the attribution of compound extremes but also be useful beyond the project. All the datasets generated being openly accessible, other researchers will be able to use these datasets to complement, reproduce or advance the field of compound extreme attribution. These datasets may also be useful when communicating with policy makers. Some of the methodology developed here could also be applied for early warning systems, either based on the same datasets or using the same methodology but with similar datasets. Similarly, the attribution methodology will be applied to compound extremes that will happen during the period of the project. This workflow, starting from the datasets used, generated will serve as a prototype for future compound extreme attribution studies and will be tested in the hackathon.

2. FAIR data

All data generated throughout the course of the project will be made available applying the FAIR principle: data will be Findable (through standards for identification and rich metadata), Accessible (how data are accessed during and after the project lifetime), Interoperable (defining sharing policy and integration into workflows) and Reusable (including clear licensing and correct formatting of data and metadata).

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Making data findable involves ensuring that data is discoverable and identifiable by a persistent identifier, and that rich metadata is provided to allow for easy discovery. In order to achieve this, the data produced in the

⁴ Paprotny, D., Morales-Nápoles, O., & Jonkman, S. N. (2018). HANZE: a pan-European database of exposure to natural hazards and damaging historical floods since 1870. *Earth System Science Data*, 10(1), 565-581.

project will be accompanied by metadata that follows the domain-specific standards, such as the CF convention and OGC⁵ standards for hazard data, and the vulnerability and exposure data the standards used in JRC Risk Data Hub. The data produced as a result of the project will follow OGC standards.

The data will be described using rich metadata. Search keywords will also be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and potential reuse. Additionally, the metadata will be offered in a way that can be harvested and indexed. This will enable national and European data portals to index and harvest the metadata, which will make the data more easily discoverable and accessible to a wider audience.

2.2. Making data openly accessible

All data generated by the COMPASS project will be publicly available by default and will be published in appropriate open access data repositories, such as Zenodo and Pangea. This means datasets will be assigned, a globally unique and persistent identifier (DOI). This will ensure that the data remains available to the scientific community. A dedicated group on the repository, with a link of the project webpage, will be created for users to have an easy overview of all the datasets generated within the project and accessible.

Should any of the datasets produced during the project prove to be useful to the wider European community, they can be proposed to become deposited in well-established, domain-specific data repositories, namely Copernicus Climate and Atmosphere Data Store for hazard data, and JRC Risk Data Hub for exposure and vulnerability data.

The priority is to develop methodologies and toolboxes that use open datasets and open-source software. Example of open-source software are SFINCS⁶ or Delft3D⁷. All libraries will be described within the toolbox alongside references to metadata and licenses to promote uptake within the wider community.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We aim to make the data produced and used in the COMPASS project interoperable within and across disciplines. To achieve this, we will follow established community-endorsed best practices, such as using common and widely accepted standards and formats (CSV, JSON, XML, Zarr, netCDF, GeoTiff), providing rich metadata, using persistent identifiers, and making the data openly available wherever possible. For hazard data, the project will follow standards defined by the WMO, CF convention, and OGC standards. For exposure and vulnerability data, we will explore and follow the relevant standards, vocabularies, and methodologies such as standardized terms for describing the physical characteristics of buildings and infrastructure, as well as terms for describing social and economic characteristics. Existing standards that will be explored for exposure data are, for example, the standards used in JRC Risk Data Hub or Open Exposure Data standard. We also intend to use JRC Risk Data Hub standardized classification system for land use and land cover, which is important for assessing the impact of climate change on natural ecosystems and human activities. By using these controlled vocabularies, we will make it easier to compare and combine data from different sources. In addition, we will include references to the datasets from previous research, to ensure that the data can be easily integrated with other datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

Our goal is to optimize the reuse of data produced within COMPASS. To achieve this, (meta)data will be richly described with accurate and relevant attributes, will be released with a clear and accessible data usage license

⁵ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/>

⁶ <https://www.deltares.nl/en/software-and-data/products/sfincs>

⁷ <https://www.deltares.nl/en/software-and-data/products/delft3d-flexible-mesh-suite>

(e.g. Creative Commons), include a clear story of origin/history, and will meet domain-relevant community standards (CF conventions).

The licensing of the COMPASS data will follow the best practice for free sharing with the public and give priority to open source and open datasets. More details on this will be provided in subsequent versions of the DMP and in deliverables concerning specific datasets to use for complex extreme modelling. Some data that will be used by the project are already under specific licenses, such as the data in the CDS. This will be clearly marked in the toolbox and other project documentation.

All relevant datasets produced by COMPASS will be made public, either as deliverables or as part of a data describing article in the peer-reviewed literature. The details on how the datasets are made available will follow in later versions of this DMP.

3. Other research outputs

All code development within the project that are not proprietary will be openly shared with users and developers through open-access code repositories, such as GitHub or GitLab. This will include a publication of attribution workflows as Jupyter Notebook. Moreover, all code will be accompanied with necessary documentation, which will be published by using open-source tools such as ReadTheDocs.org. This way of working allows for shared responsibility for developing tools, but also a further uptake of the developments in the wider community.

All deliverables and relevant milestones, journal articles and conference contributions will be made publicly available as early as possible. All scientific publications will be published in open-access journals. Where possible, results will be made early available by uploading preprints (EarthArXiv, Research Square, Copernicus journals).

4. Allocation of resources

The costs required for making the data collected and generated FAIR have been included in the budget of the project. Deltares as project coordinator have the overall responsibility for the delivery of the project. However, all project partners are involved, either in support of the overall data management plan or by ensuring their contributions adhere to the FAIR principles. In particular, WP1 and WP3 will provide details on the hazard and exposure data used in the project. The related costs have therefore been included in the overall contribution of each partner.

5. Data security

The data used in COMPASS will be mostly from free and open sources. In terms of reproducibility, the open workflows will make all data reproducible, and therefore robust. Any pre-processed data from other sources, such as CDS, will be stored on disk for ease of access, but the data will not be backed up more than necessary. However, all scripts will be backed up to be able to reconstruct any vital data should they be corrupted.

The long-term plan for storage of the data will be within the existing European entities, such as the CDS and the Risk Data Hub, if the data is deemed valuable for a broader audience.

6. Conclusion

This first version of this Data Management Plan sets out the principles for the proper management of the various datasets used and produced in the project. The next step will entail deciding on more specific use of the datasets and formulating detailed plans for datasets to be produced. The provided information will be checked against the FAIR principles and adjustments will be made, where needed. The updated and final version of the DMP will be produced by M34 of the project. This will contain more information on the storage of the data within the project, a catalogue of the data used within the project and a detailed plan for the long-term storage of the output.